

ISic3006

I.Sicily inscription 3006

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Necrop zone of via Dottor Consoli

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331398

1. [— — — — — — — — — — — — — — —] ΜΩΝ Θεο-
2. [δοσίου Αύγ(ούστου) τὸ β'] ν κέ Μαξίμου λα-
3. [μπρ(οτάτου) ἀνδρὸς τὸ β']. vacat
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645355

PHI 331398

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0839

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1962.0389

Manganaro, G. 1961. Ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. I. Per la storia del culto delle divinità orientali in Sicilia. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 14: 175-198. At 196 ph

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 7 no.15

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3006. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387945>